

INVISIBLE ZIPS: UNPACKING ZIP FILE CONTENTS AND ADDING PREMIS METADATA IN A DIGITAL PRESERVATION SYSTEM

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Abstract – An important step in digital preservation is having full visibility of content and the various formats held within a digital preservation repository, so that appropriate preservation actions can be planned and carried out. Compression formats, such as ZIP files, can be an obstacle when running file format identification and validation processes. This is especially the case when compressed files are nested within preservation packages.

This paper outlines a process implemented by the University of Melbourne's Digital Preservation Program to unpack ZIP files within Archival Information Packages in a digital preservation system and attach supporting PREMIS metadata.

Type – Short Paper

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I. INTRODUCTION

At the University of Melbourne, we have been developing our Digital Preservation Program since 2013, when our 10-year digital preservation strategy was established with a vision to make the University's digital materials of enduring value available into the future [1]. In support of this work, we implemented a Digital Preservation Repository (DPR) system – Preservica [2] – in 2020.

Over time, we plan to establish multiple ingest workflows, so that various types of digital materials will be captured into the University's DPR, such as cultural collection, corporate memory and research digital materials.

One of the first workflows we established upon implementing the DPR was capturing dissertations, which have been deposited to the University of Melbourne Institutional Repository, Minerva Access [3], which uses DSpace [4]. This workflow includes the capture of dissertation Submission Information Packages (SIPs) with multiple components, creative outputs or other additional material, which sometimes include ZIP files.

While Preservica enterprise cloud service was selected for the University due to its out of the box, comprehensive digital preservation functionality [5], [6], [7], we found that the system could not unpack and perform file identification and validation upon the contents of some nested dissertation ZIP files ingested into the DPR.

This paper will outline a process implemented by the University of Melbourne's Digital Preservation Program to unpack nested ZIP files within Archival Information Packages (AIPs) held in Preservica and attach supporting PREMIS metadata to:

- 1) enable file format identification and validation of ZIP file contents
- 2) ensure a record of the unpacking event was stored with the AIPs.

II. THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMAT VISIBILITY FOR PRESERVATION

The management of file formats in the DPR is a key consideration for the Digital Preservation Program at the University of Melbourne. As Abrams [8, p. 53] states, "[w]ithout a thorough understanding of the internal details of the formats in which digital objects are encoded, the long-term preservation of those objects is simply not feasible". In other words, when the file format is invisible, a digital object is only a collection of bits [9].

While we are still in the process of determining appropriate preservation techniques for file formats in the DPR (for example, migrating proprietary or at-risk files to sustainable formats), a key first step is having full visibility of the various formats held in the DPR.

III. PROBLEM: PRESERVATION SYSTEMS ARE NOT TURNKEY SOLUTIONS

Preservica performs file format identification and validation processes by using the DROID tool and PRONOM file format registry [10]. However, when we attempted to run these preservation processes on the dissertation AIPs in the DPR, we found that the system was not unpacking and scanning nested ZIP files within the AIP.

In a pilot of digital preservation systems, Ingram [11] notes that Preservica can only unzip the first level of nested ZIPs, which limits file format identification as well as metadata extraction for compressed files in the system. This issue has also been highlighted by Preservica's online user community. In March 2022, a Preservica user logged the "Extraction from zipped folders" product idea, which has garnered considerable support by users (as of 1 April 2025, it is ranked as the fourth most voted upon product idea out of 178 ideas) and has thus been tabled for Preservica's system roadmap [12].

Preservica's inability to successfully run DROID on all ZIP files in the DPR resulted in a proportion of

our dissertation collection being invisible to us. These "black boxes" prevented file format identification, which in turn impeded our ability to make informed preservation planning decisions.

This ZIP file problem highlights that "[w]hile it is possible to outsource key components of the digital preservation process to a system provider, no digital preservation system is truly turnkey" [13, pp. 4-5]. Thus, digital preservation regularly relies upon in-house preservation activities, which encompass various policies, technologies and strategies [14].

IV. SOLUTION

The University's Digital Preservation Program decided to prioritise file format identification for its collection and, rather than waiting for Preservica to develop this functionality, implemented the following in-house solution in 2024.

A. Overview of the Process

The process, outlined below and presented in Figure 1, was achieved using Python scripts [15].

The first step was to identify the ZIP files in the repository. To achieve this, we produced a list of all assets in Preservica that DROID had identified with the PRONOM code for ZIP files (x-fmt/263). Using this list, we checked if the asset had a metadata PREMIS 'unpacking' event to make sure that we were not working with already unpacked ZIP files.

The script then downloaded the ZIP files that passed those checks and created a manifest for the contents of each ZIP file.

A second script then created a new subfolder for each ZIP file in the repository that was named the same as the ZIP file with an '_unpacked' suffix. The script then re-ingested each downloaded ZIP file to its new subfolder.

Because the ZIP was now "seen" by the system as a first level ZIP, Preservica's own ingest process was able to be leveraged and the ZIP was successfully unpacked by the system. Through the ingest process, contents became visible, and file formats were identified. If ZIPs beyond one level of nesting were present, they would be progressively handled by re-running the process.

After that process was finished, the files and folders were checked with the manifest to ensure that all ZIP file contents had been successfully

Figure 1 Overview of ZIP unpacking process

unpacked. After this check was completed, the manifest was discarded.

Lastly, we created PREMIS metadata to record the unpacking event, including time of unpacking, the subfolder we extracted the files into, and the person responsible for unpacking. This metadata was then attached to the original ZIP files in the DPR.

B. Challenge

A primary challenge to overcome was determining how to include metadata about the unpacking event in Preservica. Our first attempt was to create Open Preservation Exchange (OPEX) [16] packages for ingest which support Preservica's own event metadata. Unfortunately, Preservica ignores some of the OPEX metadata on ingest, meaning the event information was not captured in the system. OPEX was therefore not a viable solution, and we needed to look at alternative options.

Fortunately, Preservica has support for attaching external metadata to the preservation object. After further research, we decided to attach a single PREMIS 'unpacking' event with the necessary metadata.

V. RESULT

As a result of this project, we were able to successfully run Preservica's DROID file format identification processes on our collection and now have complete visibility of the formats in the DPR. Many file formats turned out to be unusual and are not yet included in the PRONOM registry.

This discovery has led to a program of work to investigate unidentified files and submit them to PRONOM for registration. The Digital Preservation Program successfully identified and submitted OMA files in 2024 [17] and these are now included in the registry [18].

The quantity and volume of our dissertation collection also increased significantly (going from 73,258 assets to 229,846 assets) after the unpacking process. This increase in scale also affected the runtime of in-house developed scripts used to query Preservica's API for reporting. As a result, we overhauled and improved our querying scripts, cutting down the number of API calls.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has provided an overview of a process undertaken at the University of Melbourne to unpack nested ZIP files held within a digital preservation system and attach PREMIS event metadata. It has explored that while there are systems available on the market which claim to provide comprehensive preservation functionality, no system is truly a turnkey solution for digital preservation. Therefore, a balance of native system functionality, and in-house solutions must be struck to achieve holistic preservation processes for digital materials.

By achieving visibility of digital materials held within the University's DPR, the Digital Preservation Program will continue to submit formats to the PRONOM registry. Additionally, we can now begin proactive and informed preservation planning to ensure the files in our collection are well-managed over time.

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